

1. Mission model

A successful mission, lasting at least 1.5 yr, is expected to yield parallaxes and relative positions and proper motions for 50 000 - 100 000 stars down to magnitude $m_{pg} = 11 - 14$, each astrometric datum with an accuracy of a few milliarcsec.

A more detailed description of expected results requires specification of instrument, mode of scanning, observing program, etc. Consider as an example the following mission model (indications of scaling properties are given when possible):

instrument : (as described elsewhere). As functions of the linear size of the telescope aperture (l), the m.e. of any astrometric quantity scales as l^{-2} (if performance is limited by diffraction and photon noise).

scanning mode : uniform symmetric revolving scanning with Sun - spin axis angle $\zeta = 36^\circ$. The m.e. does not depend critically on the scanning mode for constant ζ ; otherwise it is (very roughly) inversely proportional to $\sin \zeta$ for $\tilde{\omega}$, λ , and μ_λ , and independent of ζ for β and μ_β .

mission length : 2.5 yr. For positions and parallaxes the m.e. scales as $t^{-0.5}$, for proper motions as $t^{-1.5}$.

observing

program : two alternative programs are defined in Table 2. As a reference example we may consider a $m_{pg} = 9$ star to which is devoted a total observing time of about $\tau = 1200^s$, or 1/50 000 of the available effective observing time ($6 \cdot 10^7$ s = 1.9 yr). The m.e. is proportional to $\tau^{-0.5}$, but depends also on magnitude (cf. Table 2).

2. Sky coverage and homogeneity

With the given scanning mode it will be possible to derive all five astrometric unknowns for a star at any place on the sky, but with precisions depending on ecliptical latitude β and (to a smaller extent) on longitude λ . Table 1 shows the m.e. of the five unknowns as functions of latitude for a 9^m star observed for 1200^s . The table gives the average m.e. at given

latitude and the standard (rms) deviation of the m.e. for different longitudes.

Table 1. Mean errors for a 9^m star with total observing time 1200^s (unit 0^h00^m1^s)

β	$\epsilon_{\lambda} \cos \beta$	ϵ_{β}	$\epsilon_{\mu_{\lambda}} \cos \beta$	$\epsilon_{\mu_{\beta}}$	$\epsilon_{\tilde{\omega}}$
0°	1.6 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.3	1.2 ± 0.3	1.6 ± 0.2
±30°	1.2 0.2	0.7 0.2	1.8 0.4	1.0 0.2	1.4 0.2
±60°	0.5 0.1	0.6 0.1	0.7 0.1	0.9 0.1	1.0 0.2
±85°	0.3 0.1	0.7 0.1	0.4 0.1	1.0 0.1	0.4 0.1
average	1.1	0.7	1.6	1.0	1.3

3. Distribution of observing time

Table 2 gives the factors by which the m.e. in Table 1 should be multiplied to give the m.e. for other magnitudes and observing times. To illustrate the effects of different partitioning of the available observing time we give results for two alternative programs:

Program A comprises more or less the minimum set of stars necessary to set up the celestial sphere. It is obtained by dividing the sky into 51 000 areas, each of the size of the FOV (54' x 54'), and selecting the brightest star in each area.

For Program B the ambition is to observe (1) practically all stars down to $m_{pg} = 9.0$ (64 000 stars) and (2) an additional 36 000 stars in the range $9 < m_{pg} < 14$, selected as astrophysically interesting and/or as faint reference stars e.g. for quasars. About 60 % of the time is spent on the 36 % fainter stars. Note that the absolute maximum observing time per star is about 2400^s (sky average), which is approached for the faintest stars in Program B. Thus there is practically no room for improvement of accuracy by extending the observing time for a faint star.

4. Improvement by averaging

It is of considerable interest to know how much we can possibly improve the

Table 2. Number of stars, partitioning of observing time, and relative mean errors for two observing programs A and B. M.e. are relative to those in Table 1.

m _{pg}	Program A				Program B			
	Number of stars	% of all stars on sky	Obs. time per star	Rel. m.e.	Number of stars	% of all stars on sky	Obs. time per star	Rel. m.e.
< 6	2 900	97 %	1000 ^s	0.86	3 000	100 %	300 ^s	1.6
6 - 7	4 700	87	1000	0.87	5 400	100	310	1.6
7 - 8	10 400	70	1070	0.89	14 800	100	330	1.6
8 - 9	16 400	40	1140	0.95	40 800	100	400	1.6
9 - 10	12 800	12	1300	1.1	18 000	17	540	1.7
10 - 11	3 600	1.2	1500	1.4	9 000	3.0	950	1.8
11 - 12	200	0.03	1800	2.1	4 000	0.6	1700	2.1
12 - 13	0				3 000	0.16	2200	3.6
13 - 14	0				2 000	0.04	2300	7.8
Total	51 000		6.10 ⁷ _s		100 000		6.10 ⁷ _s	
Average			1170 ^s	0.95 (median)			600 ^s	1.7 (median)

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parallax and common proper motion of a cluster by averaging the measured quantities for individual stars. The mean error $\bar{\epsilon}$ of the average of n quantities, each having the m.e. ϵ , is clearly given by

$$\bar{\epsilon}^2 = \frac{\epsilon^2}{n} (1 + (n - 1)\rho),$$

where ρ is the average correlation between any two of the quantities. As $n \rightarrow \infty$ we obtain the asymptotic m.e. $\epsilon\sqrt{\rho}$. It is found that $\rho \approx 0.2$ for stars closer than $\approx 1^\circ$, decreasing to $|\rho| \leq 0.05$ for distances $\geq 4^\circ$. Thus, for extended clusters (such as the Hyades) it should indeed be possible to reduce the mean errors by a factor 4, whereas it seems difficult to reach even a factor 2 for small clusters, taking into account also the necessarily shorter observing time per star in this case.